

ON SMARANDACHE CONCATENATED SEQUENCES I: FACTORIAL SEQUENCE

Maohua Le

Zhanjiang Normal College, Zhanjiang, Guangdong, P.R.China

Abstract. let $A = \{n!\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, and let $C(A) = \{c_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ denote the Smarandache concatenated sequence of A. In this paper we prove that if $n > 1$, then c_n does not belong to A.

Let $A = \{n!\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, and let $C(A) = \{c_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ denote the Smarandache concatenated sequence of A. In this part we prove the following result.

Theorem. If $n > 1$, then c_n does not belong to A.

Proof. By the definition of the Smarandache concatenated sequence of A (see[1]), we have

$$(1) \quad c_n = \overline{1!2!\dots n!}$$

if $n > 1$ and c_n belongs to A, then

$$(2) \quad c_n = m!,$$

where m is a positive integer with $m > n > 1$. Notice that $c_n = 12, 126, 12624, 12624120, 12624120720, 126241207205040$ and 12624120720504040320 for $n=2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7$ and 8 , which are none factorial. We may assume that $n \geq 9$. Then we have $m > 9$.

For any positive integer a, let $d(a)$ denote the figure number of a in the decimal system. Since $n \geq 9$, we see from (1) that

$$(3) \quad c_n = n! + (n-1)!10^{d(n!)} + \dots + 9!10^{d(n!)+\dots+d(12!)} \\ + 12624120720504040320 \cdot 10^{d(n!)+\dots+d(12!)+d(126!)}.$$

Since $3^2 \nmid 12624120720504040320$ and $3^k \mid k!$ for $k \geq 9$, we get from (3) that

$$(4) \quad 3^2 \mid c_n, n \geq 9.$$

Hoever, since $m > n \geq 9$, we obtain frpm (2) that $3^k \mid c_n$, which contradicts (4). Thus, if $n > 1$, then c_n does not belong to A. The Theorem is proved.

Reference

1.M.-H.Le, On Smarandache concatenated sequences I:Prime
power sequence, Smarandache Notions J.